

Graphical Abstract

International Student Satisfaction: A Comparative Analysis of Student Perceptions, Expectation and Reality, and their Relationship with Recruitment Policies and Approach

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Highlights

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- The study provides a framework for understanding the factors that affect the satisfaction of international students in four major study destinations (the United Kingdom, United States, Australia, and Canada) and how these factors are interrelated.
- The results highlight the importance of addressing highly sensitive attributes in order to optimise student satisfaction, rather than using a one-size-fits-all approach.
- The study also highlights the importance of regulating recruitment practices and addressing the mismatch between student expectations and the realities experienced by students.

International Student Satisfaction: A Comparative Analysis of Student Perceptions, Expectation and Reality, and their Relationship with Recruitment Policies and Approach

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Abstract

International student recruitment is a significant contributor to the higher education sector, with many countries actively seeking to attract international students to their institutions. This study examines the factors affecting the satisfaction of international students studying in the UK, USA, Australia, and Canada. Using a mixed-method research approach, including both qualitative and quantitative methods, attempting to measure the gap between student expectations and perceptions using the SERVQUAL instrument. Analysis identifies eight latent constructs as significant predictors of student satisfaction: accommodation, technology, lifestyle, image and prestige, social orientation, education, settlement, and economic factors. The article highlights the importance of addressing these factors to optimise student satisfaction and provides insights for policymakers in higher education institutions and governments looking to expand the overseas education sector. It is the authors assertion that new technologies can be used to integrate and monitor the processes of promotion, analysis, application, and recruitment to improve overseas student recruitment processes.

Keywords: International student satisfaction, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analysis, SERVQUAL instrument, Higher education policy

1. Introduction

A substantial number of students pursue their tertiary and/or further education in countries other than their own. The total number of overseas students worldwide in 2020 and 2021 was 5.6 and 6.1 million respectively and the number of overseas students has been growing rapidly, and the expansion is set to continue¹². Students select their target institution using different criteria, including individual objectives, and background, social and cultural norms within their home countries. The end goal for all overseas students is the successful completion of their studies whilst benefiting from their investment in hard work, time, and money.

Higher education institutions have been operating more like businesses for some time now. As a result of awareness of the commercial aspects of their business, universities are recognising the added value of increased overseas student numbers. The value comes from boosted revenue, increased research and scholarly throughput, and elevated international reputation. This has led to the development of strategies by universities to bolster the attractiveness of their courses in different overseas markets to achieve the stated objectives. Part of this strategy in many institutions has led to the outsourcing of student recruitment and related marketing activities to commercial operators. This is in the form of commissioned agents who have the local knowledge and connection to enhance recruitment efficacy.

However, due to the competition for student recruitment amongst governments and institutions, the credibility of the approach of engaging agents has been questioned. There are doubts whether agents could remain impartial and act in the best interest of the student, rather than influencing them in favour of the universities that pay the highest commission. This is a significant concern for students, as well as for universities, governments, and other stakeholders, as it undermines the integrity of the recruitment process and the value of the education received.

Motivated by concerns about the ability of a small proportion of students to benefit from their financial and emotional investment, this research sets out to investigate and evaluate some of the anecdotal observations. This

¹Available online, <https://www.iie.org/Research-and-Insights/Project-Atlas/Explore-Global-Data>, last accessed 21/01/2023

²Available online, <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/b9aab803-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/b9aab803-en>, last accessed 21/01/2023

research aims to evaluate the system of "international student recruitment" which is offered as a service, with the objective to highlight the machinations of the student recruitment operation in general, and in the United Kingdom (UK), in particular. By providing an in-depth analysis of this ecosystem, this study aims to identify and propose mitigating strategies to address potential pitfalls to ensure that the recruitment processes are fair and transparent for all students.

The structure of this paper is as follows: a brief literature review is done in Section 2, the methodology in Section 3, the results analysis is performed in Section 4 and the conclusions and future work in Section 5.

2. Background research

International student recruitment can follow three key paths. Governments often set up dedicated agencies that promote universities in their respective countries, pursuing government policies and targets. For example, in the UK, the British Council has been tasked with promoting UK Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). Other countries have their own agencies with their own approach. HEIs also market their courses both directly and indirectly, and some may use third-party agents with satellite offices in different territories, who may promote different institutions.

Direct marketing can be a controversial approach. According to Bradley [5], some universities in the UK have been accused of breaching advertising codes by making claims with scant evidence to attract international students to their universities. The Advertising Standards Authority has issued warnings against several universities after evaluating such cases and has concluded that advertisements are likely to mislead and breach advertising codes [13, 5]. This is a significant concern for students, as well as for universities, governments, and other stakeholders, as it undermines the integrity of the recruitment process and the value of the education received.

Student recruitment agencies can also be a source of concern. Tran and Vu [24] conducted research on how agencies affect student outcomes, and how this approach may impact foreign students' lives when compared with realities on the ground. Bista [4] reported a warning issued to students by the government of Nepal, warning them of fraudulent recruiting agencies and consultancy firms, after evidence of providing misleading information by many agents surfaced. This is a serious issue as it can lead to students

making the wrong choices regarding their education and career, and can also lead to financial losses.

In addition to the concerns mentioned above, there are also ethical concerns surrounding the use of agents. There have been reports of agents demanding exorbitant fees from students, providing false information and even falsifying documents [12]. This can put students in a difficult situation, especially if they are not familiar with the country or the education system they are planning to study in, and can lead to students being denied entry to the country or being expelled from their educational institution, causing them to lose their investment in time, money, and effort [12].

To address these concerns, governments, universities, and other stakeholders need to work together to establish and enforce regulations and standards to ensure that international student recruitment is fair and transparent [1]. This can include regular audits of agents and universities, and implementing stricter penalties for those who violate the rules. Additionally, students and their families should be provided with accurate and reliable information about the education system, visa requirements, and other important aspects of studying abroad [1].

Nikula [19] examines the longitudinal development of education agent standards in Australia and New Zealand and their role in protecting international students' rights and the long-term sustainability of the export potential of the education sectors. The study found that over time, the standards have been strengthened by adding further protections and aligning with issues identified by key stakeholders and official reviews [19]. However, the study also found that there are a number of limitations that diminish the government's ability to mitigate providers' opportunistic behaviour to protect international students. The study concludes by discussing potential future avenues for government regulation in this policy domain, such as comprehensive due diligence, compulsory and written institution - education-agent contracts, mandatory agent training, and transparency in the use of agents [19].

Furthermore, universities should establish robust policies and procedures to ensure that their recruitment practices are fair and transparent. This can include regular monitoring of agents and other third-party representatives, and ensuring that all advertisements and promotional materials are accurate and truthful [23]. Universities should also establish clear communication channels with potential students and their families to address any concerns and provide support throughout the recruitment process [23].

The Office for Students (OfS)³ sets minimum requirements for the quality of courses at universities and colleges that are registered with it through the "B conditions" of registration. These conditions include the academic experience, resources and support, student outcomes, assessment and awards, and sector-recognised standards. Universities and colleges with more than 500 students are also required to participate in the Teaching Excellence and Student Outcomes Framework (TEF) which measures excellence in addition to these requirements. The TEF rates universities and colleges as gold, silver, bronze or provisional based on their performance.

Beech [3] examines the role of the urban in the international student migration industry, showing how universities rely on the "throwntogether-ness" of people, images, and experiences to create, foster, and embed the geographical imagery in their recruitment process to attract and encourage brand loyalty from prospective students. The article explores three urban encounters in the recruitment process. Beech et al. [3] concludes that while this aspect of international student mobility has been under-researched, it is important to understand how the urban encounter makes international student mobility possible and there is still scope for further research. In another article, Beech [2] examines how performances of care are a critical aspect in the international student recruitment process, showing how performances of caring are used to secure international student enrolment, but raises concerns about the relationship between care and the marketised nature of the higher education system, highlighting the need for a genuine concern for student welfare and the nature of the neoliberal university.

Han [11] provides a cross-disciplinary review of literature regarding the workforce integration of international graduates. In the review, Han [11] focused on specific issues and themes related to their work integration after graduation, and highlights three levels of analysis: micro-level, meso-level and macro-level. At the micro-level, the study has emphasised the importance of various individual characteristics such as education level, language fluency, and previous work experience in contributing to the workforce integration of international graduates [11]. At the meso-level, study have highlighted the importance of organisational and institutional factors, such as

³Available online, <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/for-students/teaching-quality-and-tef/student-guide-to-quality-and-standards/>, last accessed 24/01/2023

workplace culture and policies, in shaping the workforce integration of international graduates [11]. At the macro-level, study have explored the impact of societal and systemic factors, such as immigration policies and labour market conditions, on the workforce integration by international graduates [11]. The paper also highlights several promising areas for future research, including assessing a wider range of work and career outcomes, in-depth analysis of individual characteristics and their effects on work outcomes, and the intersectionality of demographic factors [11].

In conclusion, international student recruitment is a complex and multi-faceted process that involves multiple stakeholders [6]. To ensure that the process is fair and transparent for all students, it is important for governments, universities, and other stakeholders to work together to establish and enforce regulations and standards [6]. Additionally, potential students and their families should be provided with accurate and reliable information and support to help them make informed decisions about their education and career.

3. Methodology

A mixed method research approach was used in this study, incorporating elements of both qualitative and quantitative research methods [25]. In the exploratory stage, information was gathered to guide both qualitative and quantitative research. Focus group meetings and individual in-depth interviews were conducted using online communication tools during the data gathering stage. A total of 36 participants, who had either completed or were currently completing their studies at an overseas university, took part in these interviews. Focus group meetings were also held with students from the target countries, with each meeting consisting of 6 to 8 individuals.

The outcomes from these discussions, along with information obtained from secondary research, were used to develop a theoretical framework. To quantify the discrepancy between expectations and satisfaction within this framework, a survey instrument was constructed and distributed using Google Forms. Key factors associated with the satisfaction of international students were identified from the results of the focus group meetings and individual interviews. These key factors were then analysed using the SERVQUAL instrument [21]. SERVQUAL is a measurement instrument used to evaluate customer satisfaction with a service by assessing the gap between customer expectations and perceptions of the service received. It consists of five di-

Table 1: Adaptation of SERVQUAL to measure Student satisfaction

Reliability	High standard of teaching with quality lecturers
	Standard and quality of academics
	Reasonable accommodation cost
Assurance	High international credibility/prestige of the institution
	High reputation/prestige of the institution in the home country
	High reputation/prestige as a university in the host country
Empathy	High number of fellow students from home country
	Social activities
	Welcoming population at the host country
	Availability of part-time jobs
	Reasonable pay rate for part-time jobs
	Security/safety
	Quality of living / lifestyle
	Freedom of speech/expression in host country
	Future career opportunities in host country
	Opportunities for settlement in host country
Costs (living, subsistence, travel, etc.)	
Tangibles	Availability of modern facilities
	Comfortable and convenient public transport
	Comfortable and standard accommodation
	Use of state-of-the-art technology in education

mensions of service quality: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, and it is widely used in various sectors to evaluate and improve the quality of service provided to customers. The SERVQUAL model was adapted to measure the gap between student expectations and perceptions in this study as depicted in Table 1.

Data collection for this model was obtained through an online survey conducted among international students studying in the USA, UK, Australia, and Canada, which are known to be major student destinations. The survey was designed using the SERVQUAL framework [20] and aimed at measuring the expectation and perception of each variable related to student satisfaction. A seven-scale Likert scale was used in the questionnaire, ranging from 1 to 7, with no verbal labels for scale points 2 through 6. Scale points 1 and 7 were labelled according to the type of question, and labels were reversed in negatively worded questions to avoid reverse coding in data analysis. A mix of positive and negative worded statements was used in the questionnaire, as

recommended for scale development by [7].

Empirical models were developed for these major student destinations in this study to analyse the relationship and correlation of these factors with student satisfaction using Structural Equation Modelling techniques. The perception levels were analysed with descriptive statistics. The raw data set for Australia had 101 samples, the United States of America (USA) 113 samples, the UK 103 samples, and Canada 32 samples.

Data Analysis was carried out using three major software tools. Microsoft Excel was used as a mediator to transfer data from Google Forms to IBM SPSS Statistics. All statistical analysis was carried out using IBM SPSS statistics (Version 28)⁴. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was conducted using IBM SPSS Amos (Version 26)⁵. Mean values of perception levels of each factor related to each country were analysed to identify the current relationship of each factor to satisfaction and dissatisfaction levels of students. The perception score matrix was developed from the descriptive statistics obtained from SPSS for each country. The difference score between expectation and perception, for each item of each factor, was calculated in Microsoft Excel using an equation. The prepared data set with the difference score of each factor was then fed to SPSS for further analysis.

$$G = E - P \tag{1}$$

where G is the gap, E the expectation and P the Perception. Both categorical and continuous variables were checked carefully with case screening and variable screening. Missing data and unengaged responses were treated and filtered with IBM SPSS statistics. Range of an absolute value of 2.0 (i.e. within the range of -2.0 to +2.0) for both skewness and kurtosis values were used to check the normality as recommended by Hahs-Vaughn & Lomax [10]. Further, as suggested by Ghasemi and Zahediasl [9], with large enough sample sizes (> 30 or 40), the violation of the normality assumption should not cause major problems. Hence, minor deviations were ignored if the normality was visually acceptable in histograms.

All analyses were conducted using Maximum Likelihood (ML) estima-

⁴Available online, <https://www.ibm.com/support/pages/downloading-ibm-spss-statistics-28010>, last accessed 22/01/2023

⁵Available online, <https://www.ibm.com/support/pages/downloading-ibm-spss-amos-26>, last accessed 22/01/2023

tions. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO), a measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's Test were checked to ensure they met the required minimum threshold value of 0.7 [27]. Commonalities were also checked and extraction values below 0.3 were removed [27]. The Total Variance Explained (TVE) table was checked to ensure that the cumulative percentage of extraction sums of squared loadings was above 50%, which is considered an acceptable percentage [27]. Extraction based on Elgen value was used instead of a fixed number of factors to cross-check the validity of the hypothesised model. Non-redundant residuals with an absolute value greater than 0.05 were checked to ensure a good model fit, with less than 50% of the residuals being considered acceptable [17].

Convergent validity and discriminant validity were checked using pattern matrix. Data sets were refined and rearranged in such a way that no cross-loadings appeared in the pattern matrix. Factor correlation values in correlation matrices were checked for a maximum threshold of 0.7 [16]. Reliability of the independent scales was assessed with Cronbach's alpha coefficient at 0.60 or above for all factors in latent variables [14].

Confirmatory Factor Analysis was conducted using AMOS 26 Graphics software. All incremental fit indices such as Normed Fit Index (NFI), Relative Fit Index (RFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) were checked for significance (i.e. values $\geq .90$) [27]. Models with Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) values equal or higher than 0.1 were considered poor fits [16, 27]. HI90 and LO90 values were checked for their threshold values to ensure the models were not poor fits. P-close values were tested for $p > 0.05$, Upper bound were tested for $HI90 > 0.1$ and lower bound were tested for $LO90 < 0.05$ to ensure the model was a good fit [16]. Convergent/divergent validity and reliability of the models were assessed in CFA. $CR > 0.7$ for each construct, $AVE > 0.5$ for each construct, Composite Reliability (CR) $>$ Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Maximum shared variance (MSV) $<$ AVE for each construct, Average shared variance (ASV) $<$ AVE for each construct and square root of AVE is greater than the inter-construct. All variables were named with shortened forms for the ease of the analysis in SPSS and Amos. Variable names and labels are shown in Figure 1.

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label
1	Country	String	9	0	Country
2	Acc_1	Numeric	11	0	Cost of accomodation
3	Acc_2	Numeric	11	0	Comfortability of accomodation
4	Tech_1	Numeric	11	0	Availability of modern facilities
5	Tech_2	Numeric	11	0	Availability of comfortable and convinient public transport
6	Tech_3	Numeric	11	0	Use of latest technology in education / academics
7	Img_1	Numeric	11	0	Image & prestige internationally
8	Img_2	Numeric	11	0	Image & prestige in home country
9	Img_3	Numeric	11	0	Recognition in host country
10	Life_1	Numeric	11	0	safety
11	Life_2	Numeric	11	0	Quality of living / life style
12	Life_3	Numeric	11	0	Freedom of living
13	Social_1	Numeric	11	0	Availability of Social activities
14	Social_2	Numeric	11	0	Welcoming to the Society
15	Social_3	Numeric	11	0	precense of students from home country
16	Edu_1	Numeric	11	0	Valuable feedback from lecturers
17	Edu_2	Numeric	11	0	Good and easy acces to academic staff
18	Edu_3	Numeric	11	0	Stadnard and quality of academics
19	Settl3_1	Numeric	11	0	Easiness to obtain PR / Citizenship (Chance to settle)
20	Settle_2	Numeric	11	0	Career oppertunities in host country
21	Econ_1	Numeric	11	0	Part time job availability
22	Econ_2	Numeric	11	0	Pay rate for part time jobs
23	Econ_3	Numeric	11	0	Migration opportunity to host country and cost
24	Econ_4	Numeric	11	0	Cost of living
25	Std Dev	Numeric	13	12	Standard deviation

Figure 1: Variable data sheet in SPSS

4. Results Analysis

With the perception values extracted from the SERVQUAL survey forms, the perception score matrix was developed from the descriptive statistics obtained from SPSS for each country

The UK and Canada are assessed using a perception score matrix in this study, whereas Australia and the United States are assessed using both perception score matrix and SEM results. The final SEM models for Australia and the USA are shown in Figures 2 and 3 respectively.

A lower perception score suggests that the associated characteristic indicates a lower degree of student satisfaction. It is critical that government officials and institutions recognise the necessity of taking the required measures to improve the perceived levels of such aspects in enhancing student satisfaction. Students, who have greater expectations in such areas (variables), may want to reassess their chosen country of choice for further study.

In the UK, the cost of accommodation and the cost of living had the largest influence on student satisfaction, with perception scores of 2.78 and 2.55 respectively. Mulrenan et al [18] identify homelessness as a hidden prob-

Table 2: Perception Score Matrix

Variable	USA	UK	Canada	Australia
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean
Cost of Accommodation	3.04	2.78	4.31	3.45
Comfort ability of Accommodation	4.18	5.18	5.16	4.72
Availability of Modern facilities	5.07	5.46	5.06	4.90
Public Transport	5.34	5.39	5.06	4.94
Public Transport	5.56	5.44	5.22	5.12
International Reputation	5.30	5.12	5.16	4.90
Reputation in home country	5.46	5.41	5.16	4.83
Reputation in host country	5.41	5.17	5.03	4.90
Safety	4.96	5.19	5.09	5.08
Quality of Life	4.96	5.43	5.34	4.99
Freedom of living	4.88	5.46	5.52	5.03
Social activities	3.62	4.97	5.28	4.94
Welcoming to society	3.61	5.48	5.72	5.00
Availability of Students from home country	4.62	4.71	5.06	4.76
Valuable Feedback from lecturers	4.22	3.85	4.25	4.95
Easy access to academic staff	4.20	4.09	4.56	4.95
Academic quality and standard	4.86	4.64	4.84	5.04
Easiness to obtain PR	4.12	3.38	5.09	3.66
Easiness to find a career in field of expertise	3.74	4.05	5.00	3.53
Part time job availability	4.11	4.39	3.72	3.92
Pay rate for part time job	3.25	4.24	4.88	3.65
Cost and easiness of migration	3.82	4.68	5.03	4.26
Cost of living	2.63	2.55	4.41	3.10

]

Table 3: Standardised Estimates for the Social and Lifestyle attributes (Australia)

Variables			Standardised Regression Weight (SRW)	CR	P
Quality of living	<—	Social & Lifestyle	0.72	5.676	***
Freedom of Living	<—	Social & Lifestyle	0.71	5.593	***
Availability of Social activities	<—	Social & Lifestyle	0.73	5.727	***
Welcoming to the society	<—	Social & Lifestyle	0.66	5.024	***

lem among students in London, and Eley [8] emphasises the influence of rising energy costs and inflation in the United Kingdom, which has resulted in a significant increase in the cost of living, corroborating the findings of this study. Referring to a survey performed by the National Union of Students in Scotland in 2022, Weale [26] reported that 12% of students had experienced homelessness since starting their studies, rising to one in three among estranged and care-experienced students. The lowest perceived scores for the cost of living and accommodation are also shared by Australia and the USA. However, the UK has the lowest perception scores for these two factors out of the four nations analysed in this study. Hence, accommodation for international students that meets minimum standards of comfort at a reasonable cost must be provided (by universities, authorities, or by private landlords), and necessary measures and initiatives must be taken to ensure the availability of such accommodation facilities on request.

In Canada, securing a casual job is the major factor that affects the satisfaction level of international students, with a perception score of 3.72. CBC news reports that students in several regions of Canada are struggling to find enough opportunities for part-time casual employment in the year 2022 [22]. However, with the temporary measures proposed by the Canadian Immigration, Refugees, and Citizenship ministry to increase the number of authorised work hours for international students (beginning November 15th, 2022, lifting the 20-hour-per-week limit on the number of hours international students can work off-campus) will have a significant impact on this factor, giving Canada a competitive edge [15].

SEM outputs highlight the most critical factors that are highly sensitive to student satisfaction, and thus, actions related to such factors will greatly impact student satisfaction/dissatisfaction. Social and Lifestyle attributes had the highest sensitivity to student satisfaction in Australia, with a standard regression weight of 0.72 in SEM analysis. The related standardised estimates are shown in Table 3.

Figure 2: Students dissatisfaction in Australia

Even though perception scores for these elements are rather high, even a minor action related to these factors with a positive consequence can significantly increase students' overall satisfaction level. Transitioning to higher education and coping with the obstacles of socialisation and adjustment might be extremely challenging, confusing, and stressful for overseas students [4]. Hence, enhancements to social activities, orientation programmes, and counselling services for overseas students in Australia can result in a high degree of overall satisfaction.

SEM results of the USA indicate the overall satisfaction level is extremely sensitive to economical attributes with a SRW value of 1.09. Related standardised estimates are shown in Table 4.

As depicted in Table 4, the economic variable of the SEM for the USA is correlated with the availability and pay rates of part-time employment. Since the perception score for part-time work availability is similarly low, these factors play a vital role in enticing international students to the USA.

Table 4: Standardised Estimates for the Economics attribute (USA)

Variables			SRW	CR	P
Part-time job availability	<—	Economics	0.68	22.864	***
Pay rates for part time jobs	<—	Economics	0.73	30.125	***

The right policies to enhance part-time employment availability and pay rates will have a significant influence on overall satisfaction.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

The study aimed to examine the factors affecting the satisfaction of international students in the UK, USA, Australia and Canada. The outcomes of SEM and Perception score analysis associated with the SERVQUAL instrument in this study support the importance of both academic and non-academic issues represented by eight latent constructs in the study - Accommodation, Technology, Lifestyle, Image and Prestige, Social Orientation, Education, Settlement, and Economic factors- as significant predictors of student satisfaction.

The study highlights the necessity of a strategic approach in addressing issues by focusing on the highly sensitive attributes to optimise student satisfaction rather than employing across-the-board approaches. The results of this study can be used as a guideline for host countries in utilising the resources to gain the maximum satisfaction levels for students and a blueprint for regulating recruitment practices that create unrealistic expectations about university education, services and environments through overblown promotional material provided by the universities or their agents' networks abroad.

The framework provided in this study is also useful for policymakers in higher education institutions and the government that may be interested in further developing and expanding the overseas education sector. The study provides a comprehensive overview of the critical factors that contribute to student satisfaction, which can be used to improve the overall experience of international students in their host countries.

It is important to note that the results show that overseas students' perception and expectation does not always match the realities experienced by students. In the past 6 months, this situation has been exacerbated because of the hikes in the cost of living. As a result, students may find themselves in

Figure 3: Students dissatisfaction in USA

unexpectedly intolerable situations which could force them to abandon their dreams. Whilst acknowledging that a much wider and deeper research is required and should be conducted, the solution lies in adopting new technologies to integrate operational and monitoring of the processes of promotion, analysis, application, and recruitment in an integrated environment.

Future research in this area should focus on expanding the sample size and including a wider range of countries as destinations for international students. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting student satisfaction across different regions and cultures. Additionally, it would be beneficial to include a more diverse range of students in terms of their socio-economic backgrounds, age, and academic level.

Another important aspect to consider in future research is to investigate the long-term effects of student satisfaction on students' academic performance and career development. This can be achieved by conducting follow-up surveys and tracking the academic progress and employment outcomes of the students who participated in the initial study. Furthermore, it would be valuable to explore the impact of student satisfaction on retention rates and the likelihood of students returning to their home countries after completing their studies. This information can be used to inform policies and practices aimed at improving student retention and ensuring that international students have a positive and successful experience while studying abroad.

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